

Glenna2 Nordic Cloud

Aim3 Target 2 Bare-Metal Resources Provisioning

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Abstract

Description: One of the biggest challenges for cloud world is to address the performance issues of virtual resources (VMs and Containers). Recently different efforts have been made to build a hybrid model where the cloud services are used to manage the control plane and the compute is offered using bare-metal resources. This report reviews four different frameworks for deploying OpenStack on bare metal.

	Name	Partner/Activity	Date
From	Salman Toor	UPPMAX	10 Oct 2018
Reviewed by	Dan Still	CSC	10 Jan 2019
Approved by	Steering Group	NeIC	11 Oct 2019

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Aim3 Target 2: OpenStack Baremetal Deployment Report

Introduction

Chalmers Center for Computational Science and Engineering (C3SE) is a centre for scientific and technical computing at Chalmers University of Technology in Gothenburg Sweden. C3SE is one of six centers in the national metacenter Swedish National Infrastructure for Computing. C3SE is a CentOS biased organisation, that builds and operate Cloud and HPC-resources based on CentOS and Ubuntu but the majority of installations are at the moment CentOS.

Due to this fact, the first choice would be to use CentOS for fast integration with existing C3SE infrastructure. OpenStack is a large modular framework composed of over 150 modules that make it hard to deploy manually. To gain a better understanding of existing options to deploy OpenStack IaaS we analyse in this report four different deployment tools.

Ansible openstack

Tested OpenStack release Pike

OpenStack ansible is a Ubuntu centric distribution, it has the prerequisite of OS and networking including bridges being in place before the distribution installs OpenStack.

Prominent problems were the frequent changes being pushed into the CentOS branch that creates the notion of firing at a moving target. Using Ansible on OpenStack with Ubuntu as we are in our node in SNIC Science Cloud does not give the same impression at all.

The main part of the distribution gets deployed relatively painless but the ironic parts were to a large extents not in place for CentOS. At the time there were entire playbooks missing resulting in missing configuration files and other miscellaneous faults as a result of necessary packages not being installed during the deployment. We continued the installation manually as we expected there were fewer parts missing that it actually turned out to be. The impression was that there were few taking the same path as us, and a decision was made that the process would be far to time consuming.

Kayobe

Tested OpenStack release Queens

OpenStack Kayobe is a kolla / ansible based CentOS centric distribution, it has a

undercloud / overcloud approach where OS and OpenStack installation are performed inline.

We only tried Kayobe briefly, but with the current backing and what would seem like a special interest from the OpenStack Scientific working group i think this distribution has great potential and will be revisited soon.

TripleO

Tested OpenStack release(s) Pike / Queens

OpenStack TripleO is a CentOS centric distribution, it also has support for Ubuntu and SUSE but the support is experimental. TripleO has a undercloud / overcloud approach where OS installation and OpenStack installation is performed inline.

Prominent problems has been the trial and error realisation of keeping the networking being in a completely flat mode that TripleO seems to prefer. For us this meant literally no VLAN's, which seemed to be one of the keys for us to get the overcloud deployed without errors. Another seemed to be using the CLI instead of the (very nice) graphical interface. The introspection part of the installation seems to be largely hardware dependent, for instance HP generation6 hardware had

problems performing the introspection, whereas Super Micro generation 7 hardware gets introspected nicely. TripleO is also hard to trouble shoot, logging seemed to generally be somewhat scarce and some logs that are of interest during the introspection exist on the node being deployed only, and being unable to reach nodes during installation poses an interesting situation. TripleO is one of the distributions that has resulted in a successful installation.

MAAS / Juju

Tested OpenStack release(s) Pike / Queens

Canonical's MAAS / Juju is a Ubuntu only distribution. The provisioning of the OS is done via MAAS and Juju takes care of the OpenStack parts.

This just works, out of the box .. point and click takes you through the selection of control plane and compute resources and a while later there it is all working nicely. We found that there are no problems if you later would like to add a module (Charm from

Charmstore) or even upgrade OpenStack releases. However no working charm for Ironic was found at that point in time.

Current status

Using TripleO we have successfully deployed an under and overcloud with parts deployed on baremetal. Now we are expanding the installation by adding more baremetal based on different hardware while also adding virtualized compute. Next steps include provisioning of Slurm partitions and executing workloads in the partitions.

Conclusions

Baremetal provisioning in OpenStack using the methods above are hardware dependant, whereas newer hardware generally is better from our experience.

Choosing CentOS as your preferred OS when running OpenStack is taking the road less traveled and you must be prepared to dig in and change add modify and perhaps even push your changes / additions upstreams. For obvious reasons CentOS only or centric distributions yield a higher rate of success, when deploying on CentOS.

Another important note is that the hardware currently being used is discarded 5+ years old decommissioned HPC-hardware, this not only poses a challenge when testing relatively new technology as Ironic but also interferes from a stability and reproducibility perspective.